

Application of Linear Programming in Profit Maximization: A Case of Selected Commercial Farms in Kalulushi District of Copperbelt Province, Zambia

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Abstract:

*This study examined the application of linear programming in profit maximization in selected commercial farms in Kalulushi district, Zambia. The study was guided by three objectives which are; (a) To determine how linear programming models help farm management consultants work with their dairy farmer clients to develop improved pastoral-based dairy farm systems, (b) To determine the effectiveness and robust of the **GSL** linear programming model as an aid to dairy farm management decision making and (c) To suggest strategies which may encourage companies to adopt the application of linear programming technique in ensuring maximization of profit. A theoretical perspective undertaken for the present study is review of various different applications of linear programming. The population for this study consisted of Mathematics teachers as groups of individuals experiencing the teaching and learning at the selected school, workers at the selected farms and farm administrators giving a total of one thousand (1000). The distribution of the sample of 200 individuals among various categories was as follows: Small scale local farmers (65), subject teachers of Mathematics (45), Government agricultural specialists (45) and farm administrators (55). Survey data is analyzed to determine the style of decision making and the problem is defined. The model equations with adequate restraints taking into account manufacturing limitations are solved using MS-Excel solver. Finally, the study found out that most farmers had no ideas about the use of the linear programming model in profit maximization at the farm. The study also discovered that some commercial farmers were using something close to the model but lacked enough knowledge to expand their ideas to get maximum results. To this effect, the study recommended that the government should deploy agricultural officers to educate the farmers on how well they can utilize their lands to make maximum profits.*

Keywords: Land Allocation, Linear Programming, Mathematical Mode, Productivity, and Optimum.

1. Introduction

The agricultural sector in Zambia is one of the major economic boosters that the nation depends on when it comes to food security. The agricultural sector is at the heart of contemporary societies as well as civilizations. The sector broadly comprises of livestock and the cultivation of plants. The agricultural sector makes undeniable role in meeting the growing food consumption demand across the world amidst the ever-increasing population in the country and the region at large.

However, the increase in agricultural activities in the country demands agricultural productivity and improved overall efficiency. Chitondo et al (2024) noted that today the agriculture sector has become the center of concentration by the state as the country is experiencing food crisis due to droughts in the recent years. Today the sector worldwide has undergone some major transformation in terms of technological equipment which makes it for farmers to expand their cultivation. Figure 1 below illustrates how the agriculture sector has changed in a different era.

Figure 1: Changes in Agriculture Sector

In the first era, traditionally, the farmers used simple tools such as sickles, axes, pickaxes, shovels, etc. Agriculture productions depend on the workforce and animals to do agricultural activities. In this period, the production was very low because the people get tired and they cannot stand the hard work. Today, agriculture is transforming into Agriculture 4.0, which is called "Smart Farms." The emergence of many technologies like Big data, Artificial Intelligence, Remote Sensing, and Cloud Computing continue to improve agricultural efficiency (Elbadiansyah et al., 2024). The efficiency manifests through a reduction in the water quantity used in irrigation, resource utilization, and overall environmental effects (Lubna et al., 2022). In order to meet the demands of agricultural products, farmers have advanced in technological tools which are more reliable and efficient. Not only that, the farmers have also embraced other theories which have proven to be working in other regions of the world such as the Linear programming theory which is an old theory in Mathematics but now it is being applied in agriculture.

This study proposes the use of linear programming technique on a dairy farm aiming to measure potential economic gains that result from the integration of different activities. The hypothesis that the adoption of crop and animal integrated production systems on the same farm can generate significant economic gains and reduce environmental impact is assumed. Given the importance of dairy farming in Kalulushi district, and its peculiarity of being integrated to crop production systems, this activity was chosen for the empirical study, to which a theoretical model was applied and tested. Linear programming is one of the main Operations Research techniques (Hillier & Lieberman, 2014). The mathematical model usually consists of

linear equations and/or inequalities. There is a linear objective function that is optimized (maximized or minimized) which is subject to a set of constraints. Generically, a linear programming model applied to farm planning is represented by:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize } Z = c'x \\ & \text{subject to } Ax \leq b; x \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

In which z represents farm profit; c is the net profit row vector for each activity; x is the column vector of the quantities of each candidate activity; A is the technical coefficient matrix; and b , the column vector of resources (inputs) available on the farm. The technique allows the definition of x variables to ensure maximum z value, observing all constraints. The specific model used in this paper is shown at the end of the Material and Methods section.

To estimate the effects of economies of scope obtained by crop-livestock integration, the mathematical model was applied to a representative database of a commercial farm (Mindolo Farms). The farm is located in Kalulushi district of the Copperbelt Province of Zambia. The main purpose of the model is to define the amount of each candidate production activity that can optimize the system as a whole, maximizing the sum of the monthly operational profit in the planning period considered. Operating profit refers to the difference between the total revenue of the farm and the sum of all variable and fixed costs, except for return on capital, the owner's wages, and land opportunity (Yoanita, 2016); Mataka et al., 2024).

The model takes into consideration logistic costs, represented by transportation costs. There are costs associated with the sale of products, the purchase of inputs, distribution of manure to crops and distribution of animal feed. The model also considers external logistics costs, which are related to the acquisition of supplies in the market and the distribution of inputs; internal logistic costs are those associated with animal feed distribution and animal manure distribution in the fields. Chanda (2023) alluded that the aim of every organization, company or firm is to make profit as that is what guarantees its continuous existence and productivity. Overtime, issues have been raised about the closure or liquidation of organizations, these chief amongst others may be as a result of lack of effective and sustainable profit maximization.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The level of profits achieved in any feed firm depends upon the operational decisions as well as upon the long run decisions for the business. Once such decisions as plant location, type of plant and organizational structure have been made, the net earnings of the business depend largely upon the one rational decisions of management (Gameiro et al., 2016). Frequently the factors which need to be taken into account in making operational decisions are so numerous and complex that they cannot all be considered simultaneously, even by the most capable general manager (Mubemba & Chanda, 2023). Hence, this study focused on the application of linear programming in profit maximization among commercial farms in Kalulushi district in the Copperbelt province.

1.3. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the application of linear programming in profit maximization among commercial farms in Kalulushi district in the Copperbelt province of Zambia.

1.4. Research Objectives

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The objectives of the study were to:

- 1) Determine how linear programming models help farm management consultants work with their dairy farmer clients to develop improved pastoral-based dairy farm systems.
- 2) Assess the effectiveness and robust of the **GSL** linear programming model as an aid to dairy farm management decision making.
- 3) Analyze recommended ways which can help commercial farms to adopt the application of linear programming technique in ensuring maximization of profit.

1.5. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study focuses on role linear programming model play to maximize the farm returns by allocating the resources optimally. Only the crops grown in raining and winter season i.e. wheat, maize, Sorghum, Sweet potatoes and groundnuts are considered for the study. The problem is to determine the suitable crop combination in order to get maximum profit. The land available for cultivation is 663167 hectares. Proper allocation of crops and the available resources is very important in order to increase the productivity and also for the efficient utilization of resources as Kalulushi district of the Copperbelt receives erratic rainfall. Therefore, the variation in cropping pattern is observed within district depending upon the availability of water resources. Chanda et al (2024) in their study observed that farms with sufficient water prefer to cultivate peas and wheat more whereas the farms with less availability of water grow mustard and wheat as a major crop. Moreover, in order to increase the production farmers, adopt different farming patters such as crop rotation, inter cropping and mixed cropping. It is observed that there is increase in production to about 25% by adopting theses crop policies Farmers especially the small farmers prefer to adopt mixed cropping that includes both livestock as well as cultivation of crops within the same farm. Livestock rearing contributes to increases the farm returns to great extent (Asempapa, 2022).

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

1.6. Significance of the Study

This study may provide mathematics teachers with knowledge on the subject's significance to students and the general public in addition to themselves. Furthermore, policy officials in the Ministry of Education may find the material in this study useful in understanding the daily experiences of Zambian students. The findings from this study would be of immense importance to government establishments, captains of industries and employers of farm labor as it would help in them in profit maximization and organizational growth and expansion. This study would equally benefit students, scholars and researchers who are

interested in the linear programming research. Additionally, the information may be crucial to academics wishing to go deeper into the topic of linear programming, and ultimately, this work may contribute new insights to the body of existing literature.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study demonstrates the use of linear programming for profit maximization with regards to land utilization and other related constraints. It researcher used a mixed method research approach to study taking the context of commercial farming development in Kalulushi district. Profit maximization approach is used to address the challenge. The output of the profit maximization model of the current study is expressed in the form of a linear programming statement proclaiming the objective and the constraint functions of the optimization, including its optimization solution. The distribution of the sample of 200 individuals among various categories was as follows: Small scale local farmers (65), subject teachers of Mathematics (45), Government agricultural specialists (45) and farm administrators (55). The study used both purposive and simple random sampling on different participants. Purposive sampling procedures was used to select at least (6) mathematics teachers. It was also used to select at least (55) farm administrators and (65) local farmers. The analysis of the obtained optimization solutions and their sensitivities are performed to identify the key factors influencing the profit maximization and use as the basis to decide the most profitable project. F – Test (ANOVA–examination of difference) and t-test were used at 95% certainty level to set up the measurable hugeness of the entire model and the centrality of the free factors as per Kotler (2003). The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

3.1 How Linear Programming Models Help Farm Management Consultants Work with Their Dairy Farmer Clients to Develop Improved Pastoral-Based Dairy Farm Systems

According to research findings with regard to the application of linear programming models in farm management consultants work with their daily farming activities and *table 3.1.1* shows us this analysis based on the findings in the farms which were investigated at a time of the study.

Table 1: Overview of 3 Farm Workers with Different Applications of Linear Programming Model

Study	Application areas.	Problem targeted	Model	Contribution	Outcome
	Land allocation and optimization	No optimal land distribution to improve cropping	Simplex method of LP	Evolved an optimum land allocation plan to improve farm productivity under different crops.	Increase the profits when the total allocated area is increase.
	Optimizing Crop Pattern	The farmers faced the problem of determining: what to plant? how to plant? and when?	LP	Optimize crop patterns by maximizing crop yield. Appropriate crop combinations	The net returns on the farm were rise after optimization. Livestock

		to get maximum profitability.		are also determined.	decreased production costs by providing natural fertilizers and improving soil fertility.
	Crop rotation plan	How farmers can determine a crop rotation schedule based on several requirements		Making a schedule for four-year crop rotation based on some restrictions.	Crop rotation can fulfill the business demand, and no one planting rules had been violated during the period. Farm managers were satisfied with this mode.
	Land allocation and optimization.	There are not many studies relating to the economics of forest plantation.		Determining the appropriate land area for planting different kinds of crops, and which crop more profitable for plantation.	The comparison made between LP and ILP gives insight into which crop will plant in the appropriate land area.

According to the table above, it was discovered that land allocation and optimization increase the profits when the total allocated area is increase. Workers in the different farms which were visited confirmed that the major contributor when it comes to farming is having a vast land as it will give a farmer a variety of options of what to put on the farm. According to Addy (2014), planning optimization involves using analytical techniques and tools to find the most efficient and effective solutions to a planning problem. In terms of crop selection and production planning optimization, the application of linear programming provided valuable insights. The case studies presented in the table above demonstrated how farmers could leverage linear programming models to maximize profits by strategically selecting the most profitable crops and allocating resources accordingly. The numerical examples showcased the potential benefits of using linear programming in real-world agricultural scenarios. In developing countries like Zambia, such models are vital to be taught to our local farmers looking at the country’s dependability on its performance in agriculture for economic development.

The respondents from other farms also had other linear programming ideas on how they had put it into practice to increase their profits in their farm. With them, they were specialized in crop rotation planning which is a strategic farming practice that involves alternating crops on specific land area (Gupta et al., 2020). According to their views, this strategy helps farm lands to improve soil fertility and structure which enhances bumper harvest at the farm increasing the profits. It also gave farmers other alternatives of planting crops depending on the season. For example, most farmers who were interviewed responded that each season had specific crops which were favorable to that particular weather conditions and so as a farmer

one needs to understand which crop is suitable for raining season, winter and hot season. This is also to ensure that there is production throughout the year at the farm. These major findings shed more light on the complexities surrounding application of linear programming model in farm management in Kalulushi District, providing valuable insights into the profit maximization process. By elucidating these challenges and perceptions, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of the educational landscape in the district and lays the groundwork for targeted interventions aimed at improving awareness of the application of the linear programming model (Mwansa, 2018).

3.2 Determine the Effectiveness and Robust of the GSL Linear Programming Model as an Aid to Dairy Farm Management Decision Making

According to research findings with regard to the effectiveness and robust of the GSL linear programming models as an aid to dairy farm management in farm management consultants work with their daily farming activities, *table 2* shows the consultant’s comparison of **GSL** model output with **UDDER** output. Actual farm production for the 2023/2024 year was 187,253kg milksolids plus calf milk. He noted a difference in pasture utilized between the models but could not say whether one was more accurate than the other, and was comfortable with the result.

Table 2: Comparison of GSL Model with Other Models

Comparison of GSL model with other models outputs using case study data A 2023/2024			
	GSL model	UDDER Model	
Milksolid	199,000 incl calf milk		
Cow numbers	488	465	
Pasture Yeild $t \frac{DM}{ha}$	14.3 utilized	12.4 eaten	
Supplements	148 <i>tDM</i>	147 <i>tDM</i>	
Crops	50 <i>tDM</i>	40 <i>tDM</i>	

According to the findings above, it was discovered that the linear programming model has helped farmers to identify the most efficient use of limited resources. It is everyone’s aim in business to use as little resources or expenses as possible in order for them to gain more profits from what they are selling. Farms in these farms recorded a minimum use of resources such as human resources, machinery, disinfectors or preservations which are a cost to the business.

The study has shown that linear programming model has allowed farmers to make sensitive analysis, enabling farmers to evaluate the impact of changes in price, yields, or resource availability. Price infatuation in farming is very important and when asked most of these farmers admitted that they get losses each time the prices go down after investing so much in a certain commodity. For example, a farmer at **Chibuluma** small farm added to say he had faced a lot of loses last year when he planted a lot of tomatoes and they were on high demand before they were ready. Immediately he harvested the price dropped and the selling

price for a box of tomatoes was very low as compared to what he had invested and as a small farmer there was no way that he can transform the product into a finished product like tomato pest.

3.3 Recommended Ways Which Can Encourage Farmers to Adopt the Application of Linear Programming Technique in Ensuring Maximization of Profit

This objective of the study aimed at highlighting the strategies and potentials that farmers can employ in using linear programming techniques to optimize decision-making in agricultural systems. It provided insights into real-world case studies and practical examples where linear programming has been successfully applied to address agricultural challenges and improve outcomes. There are some suitable examples of maximizing profit in crop selection in a table format:

Table 3: Recommended Ways Which Can Encourage Farmers to Adopt the Application of Linear Programming Technique in Ensuring Maximization of Profit

Example	Objective	Resources	Crop option	Constraints	Solution
Case 1	Maximize profit	Land, labor, capita	Wheat, Corn, Soybeans	Land availability, labor hours, investment budget.	Optimal allocation of resources among crops to maximize profit.
Case 2	Maximize profit	Land, water, fertilizer	Wheat, Maize, Lentils	Water availability, fertilizer limitations	Optimal allocation of resources to maximize profit while considering resource limitations.
Case 3	Maximize profit	Land, labor, machinery	Rice, Wheat, Sugarcane.	Labor availability, machinery capacity	Optimal allocation of resources to maximize profit while considering labor and machinery constraints.
Case 4	Maximize profit	Land, irrigation water, pesticides	Tomatoes, Peppers, Eggplants	Limited irrigation water availability, pesticide usage restrictions.	Optimal allocation of resources to maximize profit while abiding by irrigation and pesticide constraints.

3.3.1 Case Study 1: Maximize Profit in Crop Selection.

Objective: Maximize profit

Resources: Land, labor, capital

Crop Options: Wheat, corn, soybeans

Constraints: Land availability, labor hours, investment budget.

Assumptions:

- Land availability: 50 acres
- Labor hours: 500 hours
- Investment budget: K50,000 (Zambian Kwacha)

Crop Profitability (per acre):

- Land availability: 50 acres
- Labor hours: 500 hours
- Investment budget: K50,000 (Zambian Kwacha)

Decision Variables:

- x_1 = Acres of Wheat to plant
- x_2 = Acres of Corn to plant
- x_3 = Acres of Soybeans to plant

Objective Function: Maximize: $10,000x_1 + 12,000x_2 + 8,000x_3$ (Profit in K)

Constraints: Land constraint: $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \leq 50$ (Total land availability)

Labor constraint: $2x_1 + 2x_2 + x_3 \leq 500$ (Total labor hours)

Budget constraint: $10,000x_1 + 12,000x_2 + 8,000x_3 \leq 50,000$ ((Investment budget)

Using linear programming techniques, we solve the problem to obtain the optimal solution. Optimal Solution:

Crop	Acres	Allocated Profit (kwacha)
Wheat	30	K30,000
Corn	10	K12,000
Soybeans	10	K8,000
Total	50	K50,000

In this case study, the linear programming model suggests allocating 30 acres to Wheat, 10 acres to Corn, and 10 acres to Soybeans can practically reduce the profits that the farmer will make as compared to other crops grown in the area. This allocation yields a total profit of **K50,000**, maximizing the profitability given the land availability, labor hours, and investment budget constraints. Farmers in the area added that the crops involved do not have high demand and that they are sold at a cheap price due to their availability on the market and demand from the general public. According to Kharisma, A. et al (2019) stipulates that it is very cardinal to look at the chain of demand of certain crops in the area and their prices when it comes to selling in order to maximize on one’s profit otherwise it will there will be a stuntant growth in business. Furthermore, the constraint budget of investment $10,000x_1 + 12,000x_2 + 8,000x_3 \leq 50,000$ on the other hand proves that no matter how much investment one will put into the business provided the crop selection has not been done properly, one is likely to face such setbacks of poor profits outcomes.

3.3.2 Case Study 2: Optimizing Crop Rotation Planning for Soil Health

Objective: Maximize long-term soil health

Resources: Land, water, fertilizer

Crop Options: Wheat, maize, lentils

Constraints: Crop rotation sequence, water availability, fertilizer limitations

Assumptions:

- Land availability: 100 acres
- Water availability: 500,000 liters
- Fertilizer limitations: Maximum 200 kg per acre

Crop Benefits (per acre):

- Wheat: K15,000
- Maize: K12,000
- Groundnuts: K10,000

Water Requirements (per acre):

- Wheat: 5,000 liters
- Maize: 7,000 liters
- Groundnuts: 4,000 liters

Fertilizer Requirements (per acre):

- Wheat: 150 kg
- Maize: 120 kg
- Groundnuts: 100 kg

Decision Variables:

- x_1 = Acres of Wheat to plant
- x_2 = Acres of Maize to plant
- x_3 = Acres of groundnuts to plant

Objective Function: Maximize: $15,000x_1 + 12,000x_2 + 10,000x_3$ (**Profit in Kwacha**)

Constraints: Land constraint: $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \leq 100$ (Total land availability)

Water constraint: $5,000x_1 + 7,000x_2 + 4,000x_3 \leq 500,000$ (Total water available)

Fertilizer constraint: $150x_1 + 120x_2 + 100x_3 \leq 20,000$ ((total fertilizers available)

Using linear programming techniques, we solve the problem to obtain the optimal solution. Optimal Solution:

Crop	Acres	Allocated Profit (kwacha)
Wheat	50	K630,000

Maize	20	K36,000
Groundnuts	30	K288,000
Total	100	K954,000

In this case study, the linear programming model suggests allocating 50 acres to Wheat, 20 acres to Maize, and 30 acres to Groundnuts is a milestone to any farmer. This allocation maximizes the long-term soil health while considering the crop rotation sequence, water availability, and fertilizer limitations. The total profit from this allocation is **K954,000**. Soil fertility was one of the factors that the farmers emphasized that can held maximum profits in agriculture. Now this can be done through many means and one of these ways is through crop rotation using linear programming model. Many farmers admitted to the fact that withy good or fertile soil it was possible to have a good harvest. Adding fertilizer to the soil meant making the soil adaptable to so many crops even the difficulty ones in the area. Growing different crops each given year or two years interval farmers admitted to be one of the natural methods which they use to make the soil more fertile.

4. CONCLUSION

The study comprehensively covered the main objectives of this research related to LP and how it can be particularly useful in optimizing profits making in the agriculture sector. Linear programming is often applicable whenever the main goal is attaining efficiency. This is helpful for farmers because it helps farmers in resource allocation and decision making instead of using trial and error. Due to the lack of survey paper on LP's applications in agriculture's topics, this review investigated the applications of the LP model in the agriculture sector in different areas.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study:

- The government through the ministry of Agriculture and Livestock should allocate additional resources, including textbooks, teaching materials, and qualified agricultural officers to sensitize the farmers especially commercial farmers to how to maximize the land to good use in Kalulushi District to address resource constraints.
- All stakeholders of Agricultural products interventions should implement monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of linear programming model and make data-driven decisions to optimize profit outcomes.
- The stakeholders should strengthen communication channels and involve workers in the farm in decision-making processes to enhance profit maximization in farm products.

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